

Flagella-Mediated Antibiotic Persistence: A Scientific Enigma

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ABSTRACT Persister cells are multi-drug tolerant bacterial subpopulations likely responsible for the recalcitrance of chronic infections. It is unclear what population heterogeneities encourage individual cells to become persistent or which molecular pathways confer tolerance. The current study addressed the latter by elucidating the relationship between flagellar gene expression and persister formation. A variety of *Escherichia coli* deletion mutants constructed via P1 phage transductions, as well as transformants containing an inducible *ycgR* expression vector, were subjected to persister assays. It was found that any inhibition of cellular motility significantly reduced persister formation, whether facilitated by the knockout of genes necessary for movement or the induction of *ycgR*. This was observed independent of proton-motive force (PMF) utilization by flagellar rotation. However, when the two methyl-accepting chemotaxis receptor genes *tsr* and *trg* were knocked out, persister frequencies increased. While it is unclear how *trg* is related to persistence, the knockout of *tsr* likely enables antibiotic survival by inhibiting chemotaxis towards serine, thereby starving cells of serine and conferring tolerance. The current study concludes that stochastic cellular motility promotes persister formation, while chemotactic motility mediated by *tsr* and *trg* acts as a moderate persister repressor.

IMPORTANCE Persistent bacteria capable of surviving high antibiotic concentrations have been isolated from patients suffering from many diverse chronic bacterial infections, but current knowledge of which cellular pathways enable tolerance in persisters is incomplete. Using diverse *E. coli* strains with individual knockouts in, and the overexpression of, select flagellar genes, the current study has identified stochastic motility as a key promoter of persister formation. The observations in this study improve the current scientific understanding of antibiotic tolerance and elucidate a pathway by which persister cells may be made more susceptible to antibiotic treatment.

Key words and phrases: tolerance, persistence, flagella, motility, proton-motive force (PMF), chemotaxis

INTRODUCTION

Recent scientific developments suggest antibiotic-persistent cells may be the primary cause of chronic drug-tolerant bacterial infections. *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) isolates from patients with urinary tract infections, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) isolates from patients with cystic fibrosis, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolates from patients with Tuberculosis, *Candida albicans* isolates from patients with oral thrush and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) isolates from murine infection models all exhibit the persister phenotype (Shan et al., 2017).

Persisters are a subpopulation of cells capable of surviving lethal antibiotic treatment. Unlike antibiotic-resistance, antibiotic-persistence is not inherited and persister cells are multi-drug tolerant. Cells which have entered a more dormant state, characterized by reduced protein translation and low intracellular ATP concentrations, have an increased likelihood of becoming persistent (Shan et al., 2017). Persistent bacteria do eventually succumb to antibiotic treatment; however, this requires prolonged exposure to high concentrations of antibiotics not feasible in a clinical setting. Upon termination of antibiotic exposure, persistent bacteria exit dormancy and proliferate. Previous literature has identified two types of persistence: triggered persistence (type I), when bacterial persister cells develop in response to a stress, and spontaneous persistence (type II), when persisters spontaneously form in steadily growing culture (Balaban et al., 2013; Balaban et al., 2019).

Regarding type I persistence, a variety of stress factors have been implicated in persister formation. These include salt stress (Kubistova et al., 2018), nutrient limitation, high cell number, acid stress, immune factors, exposure to immune cells (Balaban et al., 2019) and the disruption of the electron transport chain (Shan et al., 2015).

Regarding type II persistence, recent research suggests that persister formation is related to intracellular ATP concentration. A low intracellular ATP concentration deactivates many ATP-dependent processes, including those normally targeted by antibiotics. This explains both the multi-drug tolerance of persister cells and their atypically dormant state. A relationship between intracellular ATP concentration and persister formation has been identified in *E. coli* (Shan et al., 2017), *P. aeruginosa* (Cameron et al., 2018) and *S. aureus* (Conlon et al., 2016).

In a separate line of research, it was identified that many flagellar genes play critical roles in type II persister formation (Figure S1). The individual deletion of *fliC*, *motB*, *flhC*, and *fliL*, which code for the flagellar helical filament, stator, master flagellar regulator and stator stabilizer protein respectively, reduced the prevalence of persisters in stationary culture by approximately 10-fold (Shan et al., 2015). The association between flagellar gene expression and persistence has since been further established by bacteria treated with L-tryptophan. These cells experienced a reduction in both cellular motility and persister formation (Li et al., 2019).

E. coli bacteria have multiple peritrichous (laterally located and uniformly distributed) flagella comprised of three primary structures: the basal body, hook, and filament (Figure 1). The basal body, which is embedded within the cellular membrane, anchors the flagella to the bacterial cell, harbors the flagellar motor needed for cellular movement, and holds an export apparatus capable of transporting proteins to the extracellular space. The hook joins the basal body to the filament and allows for the transfer of torque between the two structures. The filament is long and helically shaped. Its rotation provides the thrust that propels bacteria towards or away from stimuli. Flagella in *E. coli* are powered by the electrochemical potential of protons across the cytoplasmic membrane (proton-motive force or PMF). As protons diffuse from high potential energy (outside of the cell membrane) to low potential energy (inside of the cell membrane) their kinetic energy is harnessed by the flagellar motor to generate torque (Morimoto et al., 2014).

FIG 1 A schematic of the bacterial flagella (Morimoto et al., 2014).

Flagellar gene expression is categorized into a distinct expression hierarchy (Soutourina et al., 2003). The master flagellar regulator FlhD₂C₂ enables the transcription of critical structural genes (Figure 2).

FIG 2 A simplified depiction of flagellar gene expression.

These allow for the construction of the basal body and export apparatus. FlhD₂C₂ also promotes *flgM* and *fliA* expression, the products of which behave antagonistically: *flgM*-encoded FlgM inhibits the activity of *fliA*-encoded RpoF (Chilcott et al., 2000). However, once the basal body and export apparatus construction is completed, FlgM is exported from the cell. Upon FlgM secretion, RpoF is free to transcribe downstream motility genes encoding for the helical filament, motor, hook associated proteins and chemotaxis proteins.

The current study demonstrates that stochastic cell motility, controlled by genes downstream of RpoF, promotes persister formation (Figure S3).

RESULTS

The role of flagellar biosynthesis in type II persister formation. Existing literature suggests that flagellar rotation, besides biosynthesis, promotes persister formation (Shan et al., 2015). However, this has yet to be shown definitively. Therefore, the current study first aimed to determine whether flagellar biosynthesis influences persister formation. In pursuing this, the flagellar-specific sigma factor RpoF was of significant interest. RpoF mediates the expression of key cell motility genes such as *fliC* and four methyl-accepting chemotaxis receptors *tap*, *tar*, *tsr* and *trg*. Disruption of RpoF does not prevent upstream flagellar biosynthesis of the basal body, export apparatus, and hook structures (Figure S4). For these reasons, persister assays were performed on *E. coli* MG1655 $\Delta fliA$ and $\Delta flgM$ deletion strains, which lacked RpoF and FlgM (which inhibits RpoF) respectively. Deletion of *fliA* significantly reduced persisters by ~10-fold ($p < 0.05$) after 24 hours of antibiotic (gentamicin; 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) challenge. Conversely, deletion of *flgM* increased persister formation four-fold ($p < 0.05$) after 24 hours (Figure 3).

FIG 3 (A) Persister assays demonstrate that RpoF deletion reduces persister formation, while its overexpression increases persister formation after six and 24 hours of gentamicin challenge. (B) The $\Delta fliA$, $\Delta flgM$ and WT strains all produced biphasic time-kill curves indicative of persistence.

However, this data did not address whether RpoF-dependent genes or RpoF itself promotes persistence. To resolve this, $\Delta fliO$ cell strains were constructed with P1 phage transductions in both wild type (WT) *E. coli* and a $\Delta flgM$ background. FliO incorporates itself into the export apparatus and its deletion has been shown to significantly reduce cell motility in *Salmonella enterica* (Barker et al., 2010), whose flagella is closely related to that of *E. coli* (Berg, 2003). The deletion of *fliO*, which prevents proper construction of the export apparatus, inhibits motility via two pathways. Firstly, it causes the intracellular accumulation of FlgM, which in turn represses RpoF and its downstream genes (Figure S5). Secondly, it renders the cell

FIG 4 (A) *fliO* knockout in both WT *E. coli* and a $\Delta flgM$ background reduces persister formation after six and 24 hours of gentamicin challenge. (B) Both strains produced biphasic time-kill curves indicative of persistence.

unable to export key proteins (e.g. FlgE and FlgD) necessary for helical filament construction (Minamoto et al., 1999) (Figure S6). Therefore, the singular deletion of *fliO* inhibits both RpoF expression and motility, while the knockout of *fliO* in a $\Delta flgM$ background allows for RpoF expression but not cell motility. Persister assays were performed on each deletion strain, and the double deletion strain experienced a reduction in percent survival equivalent to that of the single deletion strain (Figure 4). These results suggest that RpoF-downstream genes involved in cell motility, rather than RpoF itself, promote persistence.

Cell motility promotes type II persister formation. The current study next sought to assess the influence of cell motility on persistence without any disruption of flagellar biosynthesis. For this, the YcgR flagellar brake protein was of considerable interest. YcgR, via direct interactions with the FliG and FliM flagellar stator proteins, inhibits motility without affecting flagellar biosynthesis. The *pycgR* expression vector was transformed into *E. coli* MG1655 and persister assays were performed on transformant strains; *pycgR* was induced with IPTG (0.1 mM) 30 minutes prior to the initial CFU count. Transformants exhibited extreme susceptibility to

gentamicin treatment; massive killing was observed two hours post antibiotic challenge. After the induction of *ycgR* and two, four, six and 24 hours of antibiotic exposure, MG1655 (*ycgR*) exhibited significantly more killing ($p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$ & $p < 0.01$ respectively) than the induced empty vector control [MG1655 (V)] (Figure 5). Notably, all transformants exhibited IPTG-independent lag phase extension during growth, suggesting that the vector transformation unintentionally impacted alternative cell-signaling pathways (Figure S2). It is unclear whether these consequences of vector transformation affected observed persister formation.

FIG 5 (A) The effects of *ycgR* expression on persister formation in *E. coli*. An MG1655 strain containing a vector control [MG1655 (V)] and a MG1655 strain with an inducible copy of *ycgR* [MG1655 (*ycgR*)] were compared. (B) Killing was relatively biphasic for transformant strains.

While this data affirmed that motility is likely involved in persistence it remained unclear whether flagellar rotation itself rather than cell motility is responsible for the observed phenotypes. Considering that flagellar rotation utilizes PMF, it is possible that this competes with other cellular processes which utilize this gradient. ATP synthase, one of the primary enzymes of cellular energy generation is one such example. Low intracellular ATP concentrations are associated with persistence, and it is plausible that the association between cell motility and persistence is an artifact of that between flagellar rotation and persistence.

To investigate this, $\Delta fliC$ and $\Delta fliL$ *E. coli* strains were constructed with P1 phage transductions and subjected to persister assays in individual cultures rather than mixed-batch cultures as had been performed previously (Shan et al., 2015). These genes proved crucial for persister formation, with their deletion reducing relative survival by approximately five-fold and 10-fold respectively (Figure 6) after 24 hours of antibiotic exposure ($p < 0.001$ for all strains).

FIG 6 (A) *fliC* and *fliL* knockout decreases persister formation after 6 and 24 hours of gentamicin challenge. (B) The *fliC* and *fliL* mutants exhibited a biphasic time-kill curve characteristic of persisters.

FliC (*hag*) knockout is known to inhibit cellular motility without affecting flagellar rotation or flagella-mediated PMF depletion because flagellar hooks can rotate without any attached filament (Silverman et al., 1974). Similarly, *fliL* knockout decreases motility independent of PMF usage by reducing the efficiency of torque generation from proton translocation; the deletion of *fliL* abolishes typical interactions between FliL and flagellar stator proteins FliF, MotA, MotB and FliG that are involved in energy conservation (Partridge et al., 2015). These strains experienced reduced persistence due to the interruption of motility rather than PMF utilization through flagellar rotation. Taken together, these observations indicate that cell motility promotes persister formation.

Specific chemotaxis pathways repress type II persistence. Considering that cellular motility promotes persister formation, the current study next sought to investigate whether chemotactic or stochastic motility is responsible for the observed phenotypes. Mutant *E. coli* strains with individual knockouts for the methyl-accepting chemotaxis receptor genes, *tap*, *tar*, *tsr* and *trg*, were constructed with P1 phage transductions and subjected to persister assays. Of these four strains, only Δtsr and Δtrg *E. coli* demonstrated any significant difference in percent survival after 24 hours of gentamicin challenge ($p < 0.05$ for both strains). Each deletion increased the frequency of persister formation (Figure 7) by 20-fold and 7-fold, respectively, after six hours of antibiotic exposure and 12-fold and 3-fold, respectively, after 24 hours of exposure, suggesting that chemotaxis typically acts as a modest persister repressor. This data signifies that stochastic cellular motility is responsible for persister formation, not chemotactic motility towards stimuli.

FIG 7 (A) Percent survival of Δtap , Δtar , Δtsr and Δtrg *E. coli* strains after six and 24 hours of gentamicin challenge. (B) All four mutants exhibited a biphasic time-kill curve characteristic of persisters.

DISCUSSION

In this study, persister assays were applied to a variety of mutant *E. coli* strains to elucidate the relationship between flagellar gene expression and antibiotic tolerance. Gentamicin tolerance in type II persister cells appears to be unrelated to flagellar biosynthesis itself. The knockout of *fliA*, which encodes for flagellar-specific sigma factor RpoF and enables the expression of flagellar genes primarily involved in motility rather than biosynthesis, significantly reduced persister formation. This reduction is facilitated by the deactivation of downstream genes, rather than the abolition of RpoF itself. Conversely, the deletion of *flgM*, whose product negatively regulates RpoF expression, significantly increased persister formation. The current study further explored this phenotype via the overexpression of flagellar brake protein YcgR. MG1655 (*pycGR*) exhibited significantly decreased survival relative to MG1655 (V), affirming that cellular motility, not flagellar biosynthesis, encourages persistence.

Surprisingly, motility is related to persistence via a PMF-independent mechanism. The knockout of *fliC*, which inhibits cell motility without disrupting proton motive force, significantly reduced persister formation. Additionally, $\Delta fliL$ strains, in which torque generated by proton translocation is inefficiently transmitted to the flagellar hook, also exhibited decreased tolerance.

Considering these findings, the current study also investigated the impact of cellular chemotaxis towards specific stimuli on persister formation. Interestingly, *tsr* and *trg* mediated chemotactic motility acts as a moderate persister suppressor. Deletion of *tsr* and *trg* increased the frequency of persisters, while *tap* and *tar* deletions did not affect persister formation. *Tsr* encodes for the methyl-accepting chemotaxis receptor stimulated by serine and related amino

acids, while *trg* encodes for the methyl-accepting chemotaxis receptor stimulated by ribose and galactose. The knockout of *tsr* likely interrupts positive chemotaxis towards serine, thereby starving the cell of serine and inducing persistence (Nguyen et al., 2011). It remains unclear why knockout of *trg* encourages persistence as neither ribose nor galactose were present within the growth medium used by the current study. In all, this data suggests that multiple nutrient sensing receptors which mediate and stimulate chemotaxis influence the formation of persisters.

Taken together, the current study posits that stochastic cellular motility promotes persister formation, rather than flagellar biosynthesis or flagellar rotation itself. This association may significantly impact the clinical treatment of recalcitrant bacterial infections. The development of antibiotics designed to inhibit bacterial mobility may reduce the prevalence of persistent bacteria within larger populations and increase the effectiveness of current antibiotic treatments.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Student V.S. Mentor Role. All described methodologies, including hypothesis development, data analysis and data interpretation were performed by Jacob Egelberg. Michael Gates, Ryan Daniel and Professor Kim Lewis provided supervision during experimentation and assisted with scientific prose.

Bacterial strains and culture conditions. Strains and plasmids are listed in table S1. Bacteria (*E. coli*) were grown in MOPS medium supplemented with 0.2% Casamino acids and 0.2% glucose at 37°C with aeration at 225 rpm. When necessary, kanamycin (50 µg/mL) and ampicillin (50 µg/mL) were used for selection and isopropyl-β-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG; 0.1 mM) was used for induction of P_{T5-lac}. *E. coli* strain MG1655 K-12 was used as the wild-type strain for all *E. coli* experiments unless stated otherwise (indicated WT). $\Delta fliA$, $\Delta flgM$, Δtsr , Δtar , Δtrg , Δtap , $\Delta fliO$ and $\Delta fliO\Delta flgM$ deletion strains were constructed in *E. coli* MG1655 via P1 transduction from the Keio collection (Baba et al., 2006). $\Delta fliC$ and $\Delta fliL$ *E. coli* MG1655 deletion strains were sourced from lab stocks. Newly constructed deletion strains were confirmed by colony polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and gel electrophoresis. SnapGene software was used for primer identification (Table S2) and oligos were constructed by Eurofins Genomics. For *ycgR* overexpression experiments an *ycgR*-inducible expression system, *pycgR* (Table S1), was isolated from *E. coli* AG1 and transformed into *E. coli* MG1655. Transformation was confirmed by plasmid PCR and subsequent sequencing by Macrogen and growth medium inoculated with these strains was supplemented with chloramphenicol (30 µg/mL). For $\Delta fliO\Delta flgM$ construction, FRT-Km^R-FRT cassettes were removed by transformation of the *pflp* expression vector (Table S1).

Antibiotic susceptibility and persister assays. To calculate percent survival, persister assays were performed. Bacterial strains were grown to the stationary phase (16-18 h). Cultures were serially diluted and plated on LB agar to determine the initial colony forming units (CFU) before antibiotic challenge at 500x MIC (gentamicin; 50 µg/mL). Cultures were serially diluted, and spot plated to determine CFU and percent survival at various time points (two hours post-challenge; four hours post-challenge; six hours post-challenge; 24 hours post-challenge). At each of these time points 100 µL aliquots of each culture were washed twice (cells were centrifuged at 16.1 xg for five minutes; supernatant was removed, and pellets were resuspended in an equal volume of PBS buffer) before serial dilution. Colony forming units and percent survival were calculated as follows:

$$CFU = \frac{\# \text{ of colonies}}{\text{dilution factor} \times \text{volume pipetted (mL)}} \quad \% \text{ survival} = \frac{\text{post-treatment CFU}}{\text{initial CFU}} \times 100$$

P1 Phage Transduction. 10 mL LB broth with seven mM CaCl₂ and 12 mM MgSO₄ were added to 100 µL P1 phage stock and 100 µL overnight donor cell culture (*E. coli* JW0031 with desired deletion). The

mixture was statically incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes before two hours of 37°C aeration at 225 rpm. One mL chloroform was added, and the solution was vortexed for two minutes before centrifugation at 16.1 xg for five minutes. The supernatant was collected, and a drop of chloroform was added for storage at 4°C. One mL of LB broth supplemented with seven mM CaCl₂ and 12 mM MgSO₄ was added to two Eppendorf tubes (two mL) for each strain to be constructed. The following volumes of phage/donor solution were added to each tube respectively: tube one: 400 μL; tube two: 40 μL. 150 μL of recipient cells (*E. coli* MG1655) was added to each tube, as well as a third tube without any phage/donor solution (negative control). All solutions were incubated statically at 37°C for 25 minutes before centrifugation at 16.1 xg for five minutes. Supernatant was discarded, and pellets were resuspended in 200 μL of LB broth supplemented with 25 mM sodium citrate. Solutions were plated on LB Agar supplemented with 25 mM sodium citrate and antibiotic (kanamycin; 50 μg/mL) for the selection of desired mutants.

Plasmid Isolation. 1.5 mL of cell culture (*E. coli* AG1) were centrifuged at 5.9 xg for three minutes. Plasmids were then isolated according to the QIAprep Miniprep Handbook (Qiagen, 2019).

Plasmid Transformation. Competent cells were thawed on ice. Five μL of plasmid (pCA24N; 163 ng/μL, pCP20; 60.2 ng/μL) was added to 50 μL competent cells (*E. coli* MG1655) and transformation tubes were left on ice for 15 minutes. Tubes were transferred to a heat block and let to sit at 42°C for 1.5 minutes. Tubes were transferred to ice and let to sit for three minutes. One mL LB Broth was added to each transformation tube and solutions were aerated (225 rpm) for one hour at 37°C. 200 μL of each transformation solution was plated on LB Agar supplemented with antibiotic (chloramphenicol; 30 μg/mL, Ampicillin; 50 μg/mL) and grown for 12 hours at 37°C.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR). For plasmid PCR, all procedures were performed as detailed by the Promega GoTaq DNA Polymerase protocol (Promega, 2018). For colony PCR, individual bacterial colonies were picked with a 10 μL pipette tip and suspended in PCR tubes containing 10 μL of dH₂O. Suspended cells were let to diffuse for one minute. PCR tubes were boiled at 98°C for 20 minutes in a thermal cycler and the resulting solution was spun down in a table-top centrifuge for one minute. Two μL of supernatant was transferred into new PCR tubes along with master mix and primer solutions prepared according to the Promega GoTaq DNA Polymerase protocol (Promega, 2018). Thermal cycling was performed as detailed by the Promega GoTaq DNA Polymerase protocol (Promega, 2018).

Data Analysis. Outliers were excluded from all statistical analyses. Outliers were defined as data points with values greater than 150% of the interquartile range (IQR) added to the third quartile or less than 150% of the IQR subtracted from the first quartile. For all persister assays, one-tailed Welch's t-tests were used to calculate statistically significant differences between percent survivals.

Supplemental Figures and Tables

Figure S1. Tn-seq data for each flagellar gene organized by hierarchical gene expression

Sources: SI data, Shan et al., 2015; gene information, Morimoto et al., 2014 & Zhao et al., 2007.

Figure S2. IPTG-independent lag phase extension during the growth of pCA24N transformants

Figure S3. Proposed persister pathway*

*For figures S3-S6, red pathways have been disabled by each respective deletion or expression.

Table S1. Bacterial Strains and Plasmids

Strain/plasmid	Description	Source
<i>E. coli</i>		
MG1655	Reference strain	Lab stock
JW0031	Keio collection, $\Delta fliA::Km^R$, $\Delta flgM::Km^R$, $\Delta tsr::Km^R$, $\Delta tar::Km^R$, $\Delta trg::Km^R$, $\Delta tap::Km^R$, $\Delta fliO::Km^R$	Baba et al., 2006
AG1 (V)	AG1 from Mori ASKA library vector control	Kitagawa et al., 2005
AG1 (<i>pycgR</i>)	AG1 from Mori ASKA library with plasmid-encoded, inducible <i>ycgR</i>	Kitagawa et al., 2005
DH5 α (<i>pflp</i>)	DH5 α with plasmid-encoded, inducible <i>flp</i>	St-Pierre et al., 2013
MG1655 $\Delta motB$	MG1655 $\Delta motB::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Shan et al., 2015
MG1655 $\Delta fliL$	MG1655 $\Delta fliL::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Shan et al., 2015
MG1655 $\Delta fliC$	MG1655 $\Delta fliC::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Shan et al., 2015
MG1655 $\Delta fliA$	MG1655 $\Delta fliL::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Current study
MG1655 $\Delta flgM$	MG1655 $\Delta flgM::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Current study
MG1655 Δtsr	MG1655 $\Delta tsr::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Current study
MG1655 Δtar	MG1655 $\Delta tar::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Current study
MG1655 Δtrg	MG1655 $\Delta trg::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Current study
MG1655 Δtap	MG1655 $\Delta tap::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Current study
MG1655 $\Delta fliO$	MG1655 $\Delta fliO::Km^R$ transduced from JW0031	Current study

MG1655 Δ flgM Δ fliO	MG1655 Δ flgM Δ fliO::Km ^R transduced from JW0031	Current study
MG1655 (V)	MG1655 pCA24N vector control	Current study
MG1655 (pycR)	MG1655 with plasmid-encoded, inducible <i>ycgR</i>	Current study
MG1655 Δ flgM (pflp)	MG1655 Δ flgM::Km ^R with plasmid-encoded, inducible <i>flp</i>	Current study
<i>Plasmids</i>		
<i>pycR</i>	pCA24N with $P_{T5-lac}::ycgR$, Chl ^R	Wilson et al., 2013
<i>pflp</i>	pCP20 with $pE::flp$, Amp ^R	St-Pierre et al., 2013

Definitions: Chl^R, chloramphenicol resistance cassette; Km^R, kanamycin resistance cassette; Amp^R, ampicillin resistance cassette

Table S2. Primers

Name & Direction	Sequence (5' -> 3')	Source
F-pCA24N	GATAACAATTCACACAGAATTCATTAAAGAG	Lab stock
R-pCA24N	CAAATCCAGATGGAGTTCTGAGG	Lab stock
F-fliA_Keio	CCACTAATCGTCCGATTA AAAACCCCTG	Current study
R-fliA_Keio	CCGGTAATTCGGCGATAGAATTTCTG	Current study
F-flgM_Keio	TGTAAGCTGTAAAGATTACCCGTCCC	Current study
R-flgM_Keio	GCTAGAGTTTTGCCATTACCTAGTTCTC	Current study
F-tsr_Keio	GCGTAATCTCCGCGGGATATTC	Current study
R-tsr_Keio	GCACCCAGCAACTAGCCG	Current study
F-tar_Keio	CGGGTGGCATCAGCAATAAAG	Current study
R-tar_Keio	GCTTAAAGCTGGTGCACAAA	Current study
F-trg_Keio	ATTACCGTCAAGTGCCGATG	Current study
R-trg_Keio	GTAGTTGACCGTTGGTCTTCTCT	Current study
F-tap_Keio	TACTAACGCGGTCATTGCCG	Current study
R-tap_Keio	CGAAAATGCGCGTCCGAAAG	Current study
F-fliO_Keio	CCCAGGGCGAAGTGGTG	Current study
R-fliO_Keio	CAGTTGCGCGAAGGCG	Current study

Definitions: F, forward; R, reverse

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